

The Catalogue of Soundscape Interventions (CSI): A global repository for advancing soundscape design and inclusive urban acoustic environments

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The *Catalogue of Soundscape Interventions (CSI)* project is a pioneering initiative aimed at systematically documenting and categorizing real-world soundscape interventions to enhance the design, planning, and management of urban acoustic environments. By leveraging an online platform, CSI provides a comprehensive repository of soundscape practices implemented across diverse urban contexts, offering valuable insights for policymakers, urban planners, and researchers. A key outcome of the project is the development of an eight-dimensional taxonomy that classifies interventions based on critical aspects such as intervention scale, public involvement, and strategic approaches, thus facilitating the creation of practical design toolkits. Findings from the CSI project highlight the growing recognition of soundscape design in urban planning, yet they also reveal significant gaps in empirical evidence, community engagement, and the standardization of best practices. Looking ahead, the project aims to address these gaps by expanding its focus to under-represented regions of the world, where soundscape interventions remain largely undocumented. The next phase will involve targeted screening efforts to identify and showcase new soundscape projects from diverse socio-cultural and environmental contexts, fostering a more inclusive and globally representative soundscape knowledge base. By doing so, CSI aspires to bridge the gap between research and practice, contributing to a more sustainable and human-centered approach to urban soundscape management.

The catalogue includes a wide range of interventions worldwide, from site-specific micro-actions to large-scale interventions including urban planning projects.

An overview of the locations on the world map of the 43 sites presently included in the Catalogue of Soundscape Interventions, as of November 2023 (<https://soundscape-intervention.org/catalogue/>)

CSI coding process example based on text snippets from two submissions (Neville Street Underpass, Biophony SoundGarden).

The eight dimensions of describing soundscape intervention practices

The analysis of the 43 real-world soundscape interventions revealed eight distinct but interrelated dimensions that comprehensively characterize these interventions. The following items (1) to (8) provide an overview of the classification of each dimension, which will be elaborated upon in detail subsequently. Specifically, these dimensions were:

- (1) Stages:** Classification as “Planning” or “Implementation” based on the time and way of incorporation into the site design, inspired by different stages of green infrastructure in urban settings.
- (2) Contributors:** Categorization of contributors into five distinct groups (i.e., policymakers, etc.) based on the individuals or groups that took part in the soundscape intervention practices.
- (3) Scale:** Depending on the urban scale, Soundscape interventions can be categorized into three scales: microscale, mesoscale, and macroscale.
- (4) Period of time:** Classification of the soundscape intervention practice as “Short-term” or “Permanent”, depending on if it is established as a temporary installation or a permanent facility.
- (5) Intervention types:** Classification of soundscape intervention types into Source, Path/Infrastructure, Integral/Design, and Receiver, grounded in the framework of the World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines for environmental noise and based on acoustic design approaches from prior work.
- (6) Public involvement:** Classification of public involvement into Formal application, Design and Management, Implementation, Assessment, and Dissemination.
- (7) Aims and purposes:** Classification of the objectives of the projects into Preservation, Enhancement, Mitigation, Design Integration, and Education, building on Cerwén’s concept of “The three categories of soundscape actions”.
- (8) Approaches:** Classification of intervention approaches into four types: Architectural, Mechanical, Electroacoustic, and Biological/Natural, determined in previous work.

Distribution bar graphs representing the number of cases and categories of Contributors, Intervention types, Public involvement, Aims and purpose, and Approach dimensions

Stacked bar graphs representing the number of cases and categories of Stage, Scale and Period of time dimensions

Common strategies used in soundscape interventions based on real-world examples

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